

DEVELOPMENTAL TENDENCIES OF GENDER CULTURE COMPOSITION IN PERSON

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the development trends of the formation of gender culture in a person, and explains the role and necessity of gender culture in the development of a well-rounded person.*

Keywords: *personality, gender culture, trend, gender roles, gender stereotypes, gender attributes, gender equality, masculinity, femininity, gender pedagogy.*

In the world's advanced scientific research institutes and international centers, while modernizing the methodology of education of gender culture in adolescent students, as well as ensuring the dignity of the student's personality and their equality regardless of gender, various foreign ideas and views elimination, it is concluded that there is no single formula for ensuring gender equality based on gender pedagogy, and each society should approach its implementation based on its cultural values and mental characteristics. This creates the task of rationally using the possibilities of the gender approach in modern pedagogy, applying it in accordance with societies with different cultural values.

Gender differences and similarities are based on taking into account the similarities and differences in the educational activities of girls and boys in the educational process. This, in turn, helps ensure the effectiveness of the educational process. Belonging to one or another gender determines the capabilities of a student. Research aimed at taking into account gender differences and similarities between girls and boys is being carried out on a fairly wide scale in gender pedagogy and psychology. This is especially evident in the direction of sexual education and the consideration of mental capabilities in this process. Gender-based education is a set of educational and educational tools that have a comprehensive effect on preparing the student for future life [1]. Today, consideration of gender differences and peculiarities in the educational process is recognized as a natural pedagogical phenomenon. However, there is no scientific interpretation of this phenomenon in didactics. It is clear to all experts that it is impossible to ensure the effectiveness of the educational result without taking into account the peculiarities of gender differences in the educational process. In particular, psychologists are making a number of achievements in this field [2].

The term "gender" was introduced into scientific use by the American psychologist Stoller in 1968 and means "sex" [3].

The approach to gender from a social point of view consists of the following: from a biological point of view, gender is defined in a certain society, gender-specific tasks and specific behaviors of boys and girls, and the social meaning of mutual cooperation. the different views associated with the

The concept of gender culture in boys and girls was introduced by R. Hof [4] and represents the spiritual and cultural images of boys and girls. According to this approach, gender appears as a measure of social relations established in a particular society.

One of the most important achievements in the field of pedagogy today is the opening of opportunities for education based on gender equality and differences. This phenomenon has special value from the point of view of humanitarianization of education. In the process of realizing this goal, the first task is to improve existing educational programs using new pedagogical technology and modern methods. Equality of boys and girls in the improved curricula, as well as the determination of teaching materials in all subjects on the basis of gender equality and differences, are of great importance. Such an educational process requires the creation of new educational tools - methodical materials and didactic developments. In turn, educational and methodical materials should be selected in connection with the means of control.

The concept of gender is a concept related to sex, and gender is an anatomical-physiological characteristic related to the physical differences between men and women. Each individual can have masculinity and femininity to one degree or another. Therefore, despite the fact that two genders are determined by nature, depending on the culture, historical period, changes in society, variants of gender types and diversity of gender qualities are observed.

Today, the term "gender" and related phrases such as "gender relations", "gender equality", "gender culture", "gender development", "gender pedagogy", "gender psychology" are often used. The next twenty years can be called the "period of gender research". But it also requires generalization, analysis and synthesis. Artificial deepening of gender relations, although it enriches gender studies, does not serve development, but, on the contrary, strengthens the social stratification of the sexes. Therefore, gender studies should always be based on the goal of strengthening relations between the sexes.

The advantage of applying a gender approach in the educational process is that it helps to take into account the interests and intellectual capabilities of adolescent boys and girls in educational settings. Pedagogical influences implemented in the educational process help to create a positive identity in the behavior and outlook of boys and girls. It is impossible to form an intellectually and spiritually developed person without ensuring gender identity in the educational process. Such an educational system should be organized based on the priority of the interests of boys and girls. Reforming the educational process, taking into account the need to organize education focused on the development of gender culture, will expand the opportunities for free, intellectual and spiritual development of boys and girls.

The use of the gender approach in pedagogy, firstly, helps to develop an intellectually developed person who is able to function effectively in social relations, and secondly, meets the requirements of society.

In the science of pedagogy, the principle of gender equality and consideration of differences should be a priority[1]. The specific aspects of ensuring the priority of gender culture are:

- distinguishing between boys and girls when choosing educational material;
- development of special activities of boys and girls;
- organization of educational activities suitable for a certain gender;
- selection of educational materials that serve to form a specific type of activity of each gender;

formation of pedagogical activities aimed at applying strict, didactically formed gender interpretations in the educational process [2].

It is important to determine the gender-specific personal qualities of boys and girls in the educational process. For this, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following during the educational process:

organizing educational activities aimed at neutralizing and interpreting the differences between boys and girls;

educate them in the spirit of showing gender equality;

ensuring that boys and girls work separately in the educational process;

organization of educational activities that match the personal interests of boys and girls;

such as ensuring activity taking into account the specific educational situation.

How each of the boys and girls will be, what type of activity they will take depends on the quality of education.

In the educational process, gender is expressed through a specific basis of socialization, division of labor and cultural norms accepted in society, types of social activities, and their social status. The gender norms and criteria adopted in the educational system serve to determine to a certain extent the mental qualities, abilities, types of activities, occupations of students, depending on their biological sex.

In the process of education, teachers, family, school, environment together inculcate gender norms and criteria in the minds of adolescent students. These views create the basis for the emergence of the first ideas of what a real woman and a real man should be in teenage students. Later, these gender norms are strengthened through the types of activities formed in students. Gender socialization in the educational process is the process of assimilation of the gender cultural system of the society in which the student lives. As important signs of gender socialization in the educational process, it is to direct students to the profession, to distribute the educational work correctly, and to determine the personal qualities based on gender characteristics in them.

In order to develop human potential and fully realize its existing capabilities, the need to take into account its psychological and physiological characteristics is on the agenda, and its effective use and proper direction should be among the main features of today's didactics. During the school period, the development, mental world and physiological growth of adolescent boys and girls are different. Taking this change and peculiarities into account has a positive effect on the effectiveness of education and creates the ground for the representatives of both sexes to fully express themselves.

Initially, from kindergarten, boys and girls play different games and think differently. At school, the requirements for them are the same. Considering the different mental and physiological development of adolescent boys and girls, it is appropriate to implement gender education based on local and advanced foreign experiences. On the basis of gender equality, the integrated set of all socio-psychological characteristics and psycho-emotional processes that make adolescent boys and girls active in society serves as the basis for the formation and direction of their activity.

The analysis of scientific literature implies an individual approach to the problems of gender education and upbringing. This means that the pedagogue treats the student as a subject of educational interaction aimed at discovering and developing the individuality of each person's unique and phenomenal.

If traditional education emphasizes the development of intelligence and thinking without taking into account the psychological characteristics of gender, then the individual approach within the framework of gender education is directed to the development of the personal and spiritual sphere of students, and this is characterized by moral and spiritual qualities. , are vital values.

Summary. The social foundations of ensuring gender equality are based on the implementation of social protection and social support strategy of each country. In Uzbekistan, social protection of the population is one of the continuous priorities in the program of economic reforms, that is, it is among the tasks that are considered a priority at all stages of reforms. In our country, a completely new social policy is being carried out based on the fact that the people should serve the people and not the state. In our country, the legal environment of the social protection system with new content and new structural structures, which relies on the activation of people, the strengthening of human capital resources, and the stabilization of each person in his "I", has been created, and a legal basis has been laid for it.

The social importance of ensuring gender equality provides an opportunity to use human potential to the maximum. Therefore, in the environment of the new Uzbekistan, the foundation was laid for the support system based on the literal socialization of the market economy system, that is, the full realization of human potential, and this process is being strengthened in every way. This creates new problems and situations. Because efforts to strengthen socialization in the society, strong efforts on the basis of gender culture are not able to show their high efficiency. This increases the need to create a gender culture at the stage of new development of the society and thereby equalize the opportunities of the representatives of the two sexes in the society, and guarantee their rights and freedoms.

It should be emphasized here that any country, even if it is developed countries, cannot fully solve the process of social employment of people only through state support. Therefore, in the new Uzbekistan the process of social application of the population relies on three strong factors, that is, state support, active support of the society and the development of the potential of the person receiving social protection.

Also, many problems related to gender equality depend on the social thinking of the society, enlightenment, attitudes of men and women to learning and education. That is, the social basis of the formation of gender culture is also measured by the enlightenment of the society and the educational opportunities of men and women. After all, supporting the professional and intellectual education of girls prevents women from actively participating in not only economic, but also socio-political processes, because an educated, highly educated woman can be a part of the family, at work, and in society. in his life, he approaches everything with knowledge, consciously and actively, and participates appropriately.

REFERENCES

1. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
2. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
3. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
4. Словарь гендерных терминов / под ред. А.А. Денисовой. - М. : Информация - XXI век, 2002. - 256 с.

5. Хоф Р. Возникновение и развитие гендерных исследований. / Пол, тендер, культура. // Под ред. Э.Шоре и К.Хайдер. – М., 1999. –С. 23-53.
6. Tojiboyeva X.M. Gender yondashuv asosida o'smir yoshdagi o'quvchilarda "ommaviy madaniyat"ga qarshi immunitetni shakllantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari: pedagogika fanlari doktori diss. T.: TDPU, 2022-yil. 222 bet.
7. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
8. Атауллаев Ф. Ф. У., Ибраимов Х. И. Понятие профессионально-коммуникативной компетентности будущих учителей в психолого-педагогических исследованиях //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 1 (42). – С. 70-74.
9. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
10. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
11. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).